

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Methyl Mandelate by Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate

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Where as a ketoester is the product of oxidation of the ester of an hydroxy acid by chromium(VI) and by vanadium(V), benzaldehyde is the product of oxidation of methyl mandelate by manganese(III) pyrophosphate. Kinetics of the oxidation of the methyl mandelate by manganese(III) pyrophosphate has been studied. The reaction is first order each in ester and in manganese(III) pyrophosphate. The rate is proportional to the square of the concentration of hydrogen ion but it is inversely proportional to the concentration of free pyrophosphate in the solution. Addition of manganese(II) ion has no effect on the rate of reaction. The rate is also affected by the composition of the solvent acetic acid water mixture, the rate decreases in increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent mixture. The kinetic isotope effect kH/kD has a value of 1.90 and shows that C-H is not involved in the rate determining step. The heat of activation and entropy of activation have values of 25.0 k.cals mole⁻¹ and 15.0 e.u. respectively. A mechanism which is consistent with the observed rate laws and other experimental facts has been proposed.

OXIDATION of an ester of α -hydroxy carboxylic acid R.CH(OH)COOR' by chromium(VI)^{1,2} and by vanadium(V)³ gives a ketoester R.COC.OOR'. Thus in these oxidations the esters behave like secondary alcohols. In view of the report⁴ that monohydric alcohols are not attack by manganese(III) pyrophosphate, it was anticipated that these esters will be stable towards manganese(III) pyrophosphate. However, preliminary studies showed that methyl mandelate reacted with manganese(III) pyrophosphate and produced benzaldehyde. It was therefore fruitful to examine the kinetics of the oxidation of methyl mandelate with manganese(III) pyrophosphate with a view to elucidate the mechanism of the oxidation.

Experimental

(a) Material used :

(i) *Preparation of methyl mandelate* : 50 gms of mandelic acid, 40 gms of methyl alcohol and 1 gm of concentrated sulphuric acid were mixed in a round bottomed flask and the mixture was refluxed for about six hours using double surface condenser. Then excess alcohol was distilled out on a water bath. The residue was shaken with aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate solution to neutralise the unreacted acid. It was filtered and washed with water, the solid ester was dried and recrystallised from the mixture of benzene and ligroin, m.p. 57°.

(ii) *Preparation of α -deuterated methyl mandelate* : Deuteromandelic acid⁵ was prepared by equilibrating sodium mandelate three times in a sealed tube

at 150° for seven days with sodium hydroxide (5%) in deuterium oxide (99.8%) labeled hydrogen was then removed by recrystallising the free acid twice from water (m.p. 120-21°). This deuterated mandelic acid was esterified by method described in (i) above. NMR spectra of the sample showed that more than 95% deuteration had been achieved.

(iii) *Preparation of 1-phenyl ethanol* : 1-phenyl ethanol was prepared by the reduction of acetophenone with sodium borohydride and further purified by refluxing over 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine followed by distillation. Manganese(III) pyrophosphate was prepared from manganese(II) sulphate by the method of Lingnane and Karplus⁶. Sodium pyrophosphate (Albert and Willson, England) was used for this purpose. Acetic acid (B.D.H.) was purified by the method described by Eichelberger and LaMer⁷. Other chemicals used were of B.D.H. (Analar) specifications.

(b) Kinetic measurements :

The methyl mandelate is less soluble in water. However this is soluble in 40 percent acetic acid (v/v). Solution of methyl mandelate was therefore, prepared in glacial acetic acid. A known volume of the ester was mixed with predetermined volume of glacial acetic acid, sulfuric acid and of sodium pyrophosphate solution. The manganese(III) pyrophosphate solution was last to be added. The volume of the reaction mixture was always kept 20 ml. The reaction was carried out in glass stoppered flask at constant temperature. Sulphuric

acid was used to maintain pH of the solution. The temperature was maintained constant by use of a thermostat which maintained temperature constant to $\pm 0.02^\circ$. The reacting substances were brought to thermostat temperature before use and then mixed in reaction flask also previously brought to thermostat temperature. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and the concentration of manganese(III) left unreacted was estimated iodometrically taking precautions to minimise air oxidation of iodide⁸. The initial rate of reaction were estimated from the plot of the titre values against time. This plot was straight line for about first 10-15 percent of the reaction and included about 5 to 6 measurements. Similar kinetic measurements were carried out for mandelic acid and for 1-phenyl ethanol. Hydrolysis of methyl mandelate under the kinetic conditions was also examined.

(c) *Product study :*

The product study was made under kinetic conditions. The oxidised mixture was completely neutralised by aqueous sodium bicarbonate and then extracted with ether. The aqueous layer (which would contain benzoyl formic acid if any formed) left after extraction, was made acidic and 2:4,-dinitrophenyl hydrazine solution in 2*N* hydrochloric acid was added, no ppt. of 2:4,-dinitrophenyl hydrazone was obtained. This indicates that benzoyl formic acid is not a product of oxidation. The ethereal layer was heated on a water bath to remove the ether, cooled, made just acidic and 2:4 dinitrophenyl hydrazine (in 2*N* hydrochloric acid) solution was added. This gave 2:4,-dinitrophenyl hydrazone, recrystallised from alcohol m.p. 235-237° m.m.p., 236-37°. The formation of 2:4,-dinitrophenyl hydrazone suggests that benzaldehyde is the product of oxidation.

The yield of benzaldehyde is 90% of the expected yield estimated as 2:4,-dinitrophenyl hydrazone⁹.

Acetophenone was the product of oxidation of 1-phenyl ethanol by manganese(III) pyrophosphate (identified as its 2:4,-dinitrophenyl hydrazone).

(d) *Kinetic Isotope Effect :*

This study was measuring the rates of reactions of methyl mandelate and α -deuteromethyl mandelate at 35°, a value of $k\text{H}/k\text{D} = 1.90$ was obtained for the kinetic isotope effect.

Results and Discussion

The initial rates are proportional to the concentration of manganese(III) (Table 1). The rates are also proportional to the concentration

TABLE—1 VARIATION OF MANGANESE(III) IN METHYL MANDELATE

Solvent : 40 percent acetic acid. 60 percent water (v/v).
[Ester] = $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$; [Pyrophosphate] = $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$
pH = 0.3 ; Temperature = 35°

[Mn(III)] $\times 10^3$ moles litre ⁻¹	$10^4 \times$ Initial rate moles of Mn(III) litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^3 \times$ Initial rate [Mn(III)] min ⁻¹
3.39	0.573	1.73
5.09	0.892	1.75
6.78	1.290	1.90
6.48	2.020	2.38
10.20	2.460	2.40

TABLE—2 VARIATION OF INITIAL RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF METHYL-MANDELATE

Solvent : 40 percent acetic acid ; 60 percent water (v/v) ;
[Mn(III)] = $3.39 \times 10^{-2} M$; [Pyrophosphate] = $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$
pH = 0.3 ; Temperature = 35°

[Ester] $\times 10^3$ moles litre ⁻¹	$10^4 \times$ initial rate moles of Mn(III) litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^3 \times$ initial rate [Ester] min ⁻¹
1.00	0.60	6.00
2.00	1.19	5.95
2.50	1.31	5.24
3.00	1.57	5.23
3.50	1.90	5.43
4.00	2.30	5.75

TABLE—3 EFFECT OF THE CONCENTRATION OF PYROPHOSPHATE IN METHYL MANDELATE

Solvent : 40 percent acetic acid ; 60 percent water (v/v).
[Ester] = $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$; [Mn(III)] = $3.30 \times 10^{-2} M$
pH = 0.3 ; Temperature = 35°

$10^3 \times$ [Py] moles litre ⁻¹	[Py] $\times 10^2$ moles litre ⁻¹	$10^6 \times$ Initial rate moles of Mn(III) litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$10^4 \times$ Initial rate/[Py] mole ² litre ⁻² min ⁻¹
2.50	1.48	1.64	1.42
3.75	2.73	0.93	2.54
5.00	3.98	0.63	2.50

Py = Pyrophosphate

TABLE—4 VARIATION OF pH IN METHYL MANDELATE

Solvent : 40 percent acetic acid ; 60 percent water (v/v).
[Mn(III)] = $3.39 \times 10^{-2} M$; [Pyrophosphate] = $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$
[Ester] = $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$; Temperature = 35°

pH	$10^4 \times$ Initial rate moles of Mn(III) litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	[H ⁺] moles litre ⁻¹	$10^4 \times$ Initial rate/[H ⁺] ² litre ⁻¹ mole ⁻² min ⁻¹
0.30	1.920	0.501	7.55
0.45	1.090	0.355	8.60
0.60	0.514	0.251	8.13
0.75	0.205	0.178	6.50

of methyl mandelate (Table 2). The reaction is not affected by the addition of manganese(II). The reaction was studied at various pH in the pH range 0.30 to 0.75. The rate is proportional to square of the hydrogen ion concentration (Table 4). The reaction is retarded by the addition of pyrophosphate. It is found that the product of rate

TABLE—5 VARIATION OF RATE WITH PERCENTAGE ACETIC ACID IN METHYL MANDELATE

[Ester]= $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$; [Pyrophosphate]= $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$
 [Mn(II)]= $3.39 \times 10^{-3} M$; pH=0.3; Temperature=35°

Percentage acetic acid (v/v)	$10^4 \times$ Initial rate moles of Mn(III) litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
30	2.23
40	1.91
50	1.49
60	1.17

and the free pyrophosphate concentration is constant. The reaction is dependent on the solvent composition. The rate decreases with increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent mixture. A plot of initial rate against percentage of the acetic

Fig. 1. Effect of percentage Acetic acid on initial rate oxidation of methyl mandelate by manganese(II) pyrophosphate.

acid in the solvent mixture is straight line with negative slope (Fig. 1). The reaction was studied at different temperature in the range 30° to 45° (cf. Table 6). A plot of log (initial rate) against inverse

TABLE—6 EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

Solvent : 40 per cent acetic acid ; 60 percent water (v/v).
 [Mn(III)]= $3.39 \times 10^{-3} M$; [Pyrophosphate]= $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$
 [Ester]= $3.5 \times 10^{-2} M$; pH=0.3

Temperature °k	$10^4 \times$ Initial rate mole of Mn(III) litre ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger k.cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
303	1.004	25.0	
308	1.920		
313	3.460		
318	7.280		+15.0

of absolute temperature gives a straight line. Thus Arrhenius equation is valid. Heat of activation and entropy of activation for the reaction estimated from the data in Table 6 have values of 25.0 k.cals. mole⁻¹ and +15.0 e.u. respectively.

The value of k_H/k_D for methyl mandelate is found to be 1.90 at (35°). This can not be primary kinetic isotope effect since the C-H bond fission would lead to the formation of ketoester. It is therefore, appears that the kinetic isotope effect observed in the present case is a secondary kinetic isotope effect which is known to have a values of 1-2⁵.

A study of the hydrolysis of methyl mandelate under the experimental condition, shows that the methyl mandelate is not appreciably hydrolysed under the conditions used for kinetic studies. Further the rate of oxidation of 1-phenyl ethanol, methyl mandelate and mandelic acid follows the order mandelic-acid > methyl mandelate > 1-phenyl ethanol. These results find a satisfactory explanation on the basis of following mechanism.

much greater than that of 1-phenyl ethanol but is less than that of mandelic acid, suggests the importance of chelate complex formation, in these oxidations. That chelate formation may result in the increased rate of oxidation, has also been observed in the case of oxidation of ketones and hydroxy ketones by vanadium(V). Thus with vanadium (V), the hydroxy ketone is oxidised about 200 times much rapidly¹². It has been observed (Duke¹³) that chelation of the type postulated in equation (1) leads to a lowering of the activation energy for the C-C fission process by some 25-30 k.cals. mole⁻¹ and facilitates C-C fission. The reactivity of methyl mandelate relative to that of 1-phenyl ethanol (secondary alcohol), may, therefore, be treated to the ability of methyl mandelate to form chelate complex with manganese(III) pyrophosphate.

It is instructive to compare the behaviour of manganese(III) pyrophosphate in these oxidations with those of chromium(VI) and vanadium(V). Oxidation of methyl-mandelate with chromium (VI) and with vanadium(V) gives the corresponding ketoester by C-H fission in the rate determining step (Jain¹⁴; Sharma¹⁵). By contrast the oxidation of methyl mandelate by manganese(III) pyrophosphate gives benzaldehyde by C-C fission in the rate determining step. Bakore and Narain¹⁶ have shown that a distinction can be made between systems involving C-H fission and those involving C-C fission in the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by chromium (VI) on the basis of over all entropy of activation also (cf. McAuley¹⁷). The thermodynamic parameters reported in Table 7 are consistent with

TABLE—7 THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF METHYL MANDELATE.

Oxidant	$\Delta\ddot{H}^\ddagger$ k.cal.mole ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.	Ref
Chromium (VI)	12.6	-26.3	(14)
Vanadium(V)	11.4	-25.5	(15)
Manganese(III)- pyrophosphate.	25.0	+15.0	present work.

these views. Thus whereas chromium(VI) and vanadium(V) function as two electron oxidant for the methyl-mandelate; manganese(III) pyrophosphate functions as one electron oxidant. Thus oxidation of the methyl mandelate can be used to distinguish between one electron and two electron oxidants.

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